

NATURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EXPRESSING SIGN AFFIXES

-cha/larcha/chasiga, -an, -ona

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***Annotation.** The article explores invariable words with independent meanings, i.e. adverbs, specifically, their etymological structure. The morphological, semantic nature of words formed as an adverb is also highlighted. The possibilities of the affixes -cha/-ларча/часига, -ан, -она in word formation, the nature of the words associated with these affixes, the features of each affix in language and speech are thoroughly studied and classified. Subsequent research has provided detailed information on the affixes -cha/-ларча/часига, -ан, -она, word formation possibility of which today are denied, their formation of new words, some usual and occasional constructions related to these affixes are analyzed. Each theoretical view is verified by examples.*

***Key words:** invariable word, occasional use, pleonasm, adverbialization, simplification, semantic criterion, grammatical criterion, speech construction, word formation model, root and derived affix, word formation possibility.*

Introduction. Although the adverb is a relatively “junior” category, many ancient elements (word-forming, form-forming suffixes) have been preserved in this group. This leads to the complexity of the structure of the word group of the adverbs, resulting in conflicting interpretations. Ancient suffixes in the adverbs preserved in Turkic languages have been studied in Turkology and Uzbek linguistics. Especially, it has been studied in detail in the works of such scientists as N.A Baskakov [2], N.K Dmitriev [4], A. Gulomov [3], V. Kotvich [6]. The results of this research are summarized in the fundamental grammar of the Uzbek language by A.N Kononov [5], in the work of A.M. Shcherbak [9]

The affix -cha, which occurs in the form of the adverbs, is interpreted in most sources, especially in the "Grammar of the Uzbek language" as an active adverb-forming affix [10,529]. Indeed, in modern linguistics, the view of the suffix -cha (adverbs) as derived words has changed, the possibility of word-formation of the morpheme -cha has been rejected [7; 12]. However, despite the interpretations and classifications expressed, the acknowledgment of the affix -cha has not been

satisfactory in modern linguistics. The same can be said about the affixes -larcha, -chasiga. The semantic, grammatical criteria of these morphemes are not defined.

The suffix -cha is found in all Turkic languages with some phonetic differences. Turkologist N.K.Dmitriev writes about the etymology of the origin of the affix -cha: When the -chak element receded from its original meaning and began to be used as an auxiliary grammatical element, it also lost its stable form, and as a result of the fall of -k, the vowel sounds in its composition also changed, and the -cha /-che phonetic variant was formed instead of the -chak form.[4,47].

-cha and -chacha affixes, developed on its basis, are linguistic units that have been developing over the centuries, have the ability to combine into many words and to form a variety of meanings [1,45]. At this point, we would like to make some more comments while developing the points made.

It is observed that the basis for the formation of words with the affixes -cha, -larcha, -chasiga is the person, the various qualities of the person - nationality, kinship, age, occupation, horses, object names, adjectives. For example: *yigitcha, o'zbekcha, qilcha, tirnoqcha, ochiqcha; akalarcha, otalarcha, kattalarcha, dehqonlarcha; o'zbekchasiga, eskichasiga, yangichasiga, qassobchasiga, yaponchasiga*, etc. Words such as the ones formed with the affixes -cha, -larcha, -chasiga, which represent the sign, are dominated by the position of the -cha affix in the semantic expression. More precisely, complex forms such as -larcha, -chasiga also emerged through the affix -cha as a product of the evolution of language. Therefore, before talking about the affixes -larcha, -chasiga, it is necessary to pay attention to the affix -cha and its grammatical nature.

The polyfunctionality of adverb-forming suffix -cha, which has caused the most controversy among form-forming affixes, has led to some confusion in grammar. The polyfunctionality of the affix -cha can be an indication of its antiquity. Dictionaries contain the following words with the suffix -cha: *o'zgacha, yevropacha, farg'onacha, o'rtacha, qisqacha, tubandagicha, keragicha, odatdagicha, o'shandayligicha, butunligicha, avvalgicha, qadimgicha, yangicha, o'zicha, o'shandayicha, butunlayicha, atroflicha, tegishlicha, butunicha, to'g'rilikcha, yaxshilikcha, osonlikcha, keyincha, ko'pincha, yashirincha, o'g'rincha, aksincha, vaqtincha, tegishincha* [11,30-31].

Importantly, the affix -cha is not a word-former in a number of forms, but a form in the loading function (emphasis, reinforcement meaning). For example, *yashirincha, ochiqcha, ortiqcha, qisqacha, buguncha, hozircha, butunicha*. The fact that the suffix -cha can appear without a sign in words such as *yashirincha uchrashuv – yashirin uchrashmoq, ochiqcha gaplashmoq – ochiq gaplashmoq, buguncha sabr qilmoq –*

bugun sabr qilmoq, etc. also casts a shadow on the word-forming nature of this affix in similar words. The above examples are intended to indicate the action sign together with the -cha morpheme. This is the reason why these words are considered to be artificial adverbs. In the words “*hozircha, buguncha*” -cha has been used to denote the norm of time. For the same reason prof. Sh.Rahmatullaev considers this suffix as an affix (form of analogy) forming a lexical form [7,206]. The fact that words such as “*yashirincha*”, “*ochiqcha*” equate to grammatical meaning in the form of “*yashirin tarzda*”, “*ochiq holda*” also indicates that this auxiliary morpheme is not constructive in the same words.

The next case is that a series of adverbs with the -cha affix can only be historically separated into a base and a suffix. In particular, “*ancha, picha, o‘larcha, buncha, shuncha, o‘shancha, aksincha*”, cannot be divided into morphemes on the basis of modern linguistic laws. More precisely, words that have undergone such an adverbialization phenomenon cannot have a word-forming basis and a word-forming content from the point of view of synchronous linguistics. These words should be considered as a product of simplification.

In textbooks and manuals there are a number of other words related to the affix -cha (For example: *do‘stcha, dushmancha, keyincha, o‘g‘richa, erkakcha, ayyorcha*, etc., unstressed -cha), as the linguist Y.Tojiev rightly points out [8], they cannot be called artificial words at the level of literary language norms. The abnormality can be prevented only when these words in this occasional usage are used in “*do‘stlarcha, dushmanlarcha, ayyorlarcha, erkaklarcha, xotinklarcha*” way.

The question arises. Can the affix -cha form a type of construction in the pure sense? It is necessary to take into account two types of word formation (pattern). In our opinion, this is the case with word formation:

1. [object name + cha = quantitative adverbs]. This group of word-formation patterns includes *qilcha, tirnoqcha, zarracha*, as well as relatively new, spoken speech constructions such as *qishloqcha, qushcha, binocha, shaharcha, tog‘cha, vagoncha, samolyotcha*, and so on. etc. can be cited as an example.

2. [name of a particular people / nation / place + cha = status meaningful adverbs]. This template can make dozens or even hundreds of new words. In particular, *toshkentcha, buxorocho, samarqandcha, g‘ijduvoncha, andijoncha, shofirkoncha, g‘uzorcha, xitoycha, turkcha, afrikacha*, etc. This word-formation pattern is so productive that it is possible to create a new word with as many peoples, nations, peoples as there are cities (districts, neighborhoods...) in the world. This means that this pattern can produce an infinite number of speech products: *andijonchasiga raqsga tushmoq, buxorocho kurashmoq, guruzincha kuylamoq*, and so on.

Derivatives of the second word-formation pattern are synonymous (grammatical synonymy) with words formed with the affix -chasiga: *andijoncha* – *andijonchasiga*, *farg'onacha* – *farg'onachasiga*, *buxorocha* – *buxorochasiga*, *ispancha* – *ispanchasiga*. The -siga element in the second pair of this usage came to be used pleonastically to reinforce meaning.

Both mold products can be artificial words. The main evidence of their artificiality is that the meaning of the words *zarracha*, *tirnoqcha*, *vagoncha*, *buxorocha*, *toshkentcha* can be based on the meaning of the words *zarra*, *tirnoq*, *vagon*, *buxoro*, *toshkent* and the suffix -cha. Furthermore, the existence of a denotative semantic difference between word formation and derivation, which is another basic law of derivation in these words, also indicates their artificial vocabulary. From this point of view, the above mold products can be considered as objectionable artificial adverbs.

Certain words (*do'stcha*, *dushmancha*, *ayyorcha*, *mug'ambircha*, etc.) that are formed for the expression of a sign and whose use seems unnatural to the listener form a normative use type only if they are formed with the -larcha affix (*do'stlarcha*, *dushmanlarcha*, *ayyorlarcha*, *mug'ambirlarcha*). Because in the affix -larcha the meaning of the plural form -lar is felt. For example, in the phrase *yigitlarcha mehnat qilmoq* (to work like a young man), there is an expression that is “common to all young men”.

The semantic and grammatical completeness of the -larcha affix is determined by a long historical development. This affix activity continues to serve to create thousands of new speech constructions (author's neologisms). Examples are *ruslarcha*, *ispanlarcha*, *hindularcha*, *samuraylarcha*, *gruzinlarcha*, *moldovanlarcha*. We observe:

1. *U bir umr samuraylarcha yashadi, eng so'ngi damgacha.* (Z.Kholov, “Ma'rifat” newspaper)

2. *2003-yilda ushbu kenja turlar hindularcha yo'lbars deb nomlangan*, this subspecies was called the Indian tiger. (From the newspaper) According to the words with affixes in the given examples, they can be evaluated as new speech artificial words. -larcha is added to the names of different peoples (elat, millat) and deviates from the subject sign and acquires the meaning of the sign-feature.

The affix of -chasiga also forms words used for character expression. In the reverse dictionary [11], the basis of word formation in six of the eight words with this affix (*mardchasiga*, *tentakchasiga*, *komsomolchasiga*, *chalqanchasiga*, *o'g'rinchasiga*, *dehqonchasiga*, *soldatchasiga*, *ochiqchasiga*) consists of personal names. In words such as “*ochiqchasiga*”, “*chalqanchasiga*”, which is not the name of the person, the affix -chasiga came as a function of particle (strengthening the meaning).

The -chasiga affix is by nature both a -cha affix and a -larcha affix. This is the case for *andijonchasiga*, *ispanchasiga*, *buxorochasiga*, *toshkentchasiga*, *fearg'onachasiga*, *qirg'izchasiga*, *uyg'urchasiga*, *armanchasiga* and so on. It can be seen in the fact that words can be the product of a pattern [to a particular people / nation / place name + chasiga = case-meaning adverbs]. The use of examples like the above does not cause any confusion for the representatives of this language. Just as the people of our language accept the word "andijonchasiga" without objection, they also accept words such *ispanchasiga*, *buxorochasiga*, *toshkentchasiga*, and use them as needed.

Assimilation from one language to another is a characteristic not only of lexemes but also of affix morphemes. The acquisition of words and affixes is valued as a product of social necessity. In the Uzbek language, the affixes -an, -ona are also given. These affixes are interpreted as formative. But ideas about their nature have passed from one source to another almost unchanged over the years.

In the Uzbek lexical layer, such kind of words related to the affix -an were observed: *taqriban*, *tarkiban*, *qalban*... [11,119-121].

It is difficult to call these words artificial in the pure sense. Because the basis of this cannot be limited to a specific set of words of a spiritual type. In the examples given, the part before the -an affix consists of both nouns (*vijdon*, *ruh*, *fikran*, *zohir*), as well as adjectives (*takror*, *xolis*, *qat'iy*), and words that have no meaning (*ayn+an*, *taqrib+an*). Nouns are different in meaning. In addition, this mold has not (accidentally) created any new inventions in recent years. This evidence suggests that words with the -an affix should be taken as derivations in the Uzbek language. During the gradual development of the lexical layer of the Uzbek language, about 50 words containing the -an element passed directly from Arabic or through Persian-Tajik.

In words with the affix -an, the activity of both the first part of the word-formation pattern (lexical morpheme – lexeme, which is the basis of word-formation) and the second part (suffix-lexeme, which changes the meaning of the lexeme) is very limited. More precisely, in order for the affix -an to form a new speech product, a certain Arabic word must first appear, so that the pattern "comes to life" and the process of processing begins.

So, since the -an affix cannot form a specific word-formation pattern in the Uzbek language and is used in speech as ready-made lexemes, it means that all units with the -an affix should be considered as root words. Their division into bases and affixes should be based on the scientific views of the "word sharing language" (Arabic) and not in terms of the "word taker" (Uzbek).

About 80 words formed from the Persian-Tajik language with the affix -ona are used in our speech. These are: *beadabona*, *adabona*, *muhibbona*, *g'oyibona*, *g'olibona*... [11,22-24]. The use of such words varies.

The acquisition of the suffix -ona in our language dates back to later times. In contrast to the -an elemental words, the basis for the construction of -ona suffixes is characterized by the fact that they have words in a certain strict meaning group. Adjectives and nouns are the basis for making words with the affix of -ona. Therefore, the words listed above can be considered as derivatives of the pattern [adjective /noun +ona= adverbs of manner]. The products of this mold are not limited to the above words. In the speech of the Uzbek people, *sharqona*, *o'zbekona*, *turkona*, *alpona*, *qodirona*, etc. are used. words such as Linguist A.Khojiev states that such words (including *sayrona*, *shekspirona*) are occasional (speech) construction. According to the scientist, such fabrication is artificial and does not obey the normative state of fabrication. [12,44]. In our opinion, any artificial word may at first be individualized and seem unnatural to the listener. This can be explained as follows. For example, when comparing group 1 artificial words (language units) such as *ishchi*, *suvchi*, *nonchi*, *temirchi* with group 2 words (speech units) such as *ananaschi*, *bananchi*, *paynetchi*, the abnormality of group 2 speech constructions is felt. After all, over time, it is natural that such occasional constructions become long. This can be linked to the sociality of the language. It is clear that speech constructions such as *qodirona* (pathos), *qahhorona*, *shekspirona* or *yusufona* (method) seemed unnatural to the listener in the first period. However, every artificial word occurs because of the product of need.

Here are some examples: 1) *G'afur G'ulom bejizga "qahhorona qisqalik" iborasini ishlatmagan. Abdulla Qahhor bir varaqlik hikoyalariga ham butun kitoblarning zalvorli yukini jo qila olgan.* (K.Azzamov) 2) *Sharq va G'arbda yashab o'tgan ko'plab mutafakkirlar asarlarida ham "navoiyona" donishmandlikni ko'ramiz.* (R.Jabborov)

It turns out that the -ona affix can create new constructions from person names. Hence, there is reason to conclude that the [person name mother = case forms] pattern continues to function. The -ona affix, unlike the -an affix, can form words not only from its own language units (Persian-Tajik words), but also from other language lexemes. For example: *chexovona*, *shekspirona*, *gogolona*, etc. Let's look at an example: *Bularning barchasiga chexovona nozik istehzo mavjud.* (S.Saidmurodov)

Conclusion. Based on the above considerations, the following conclusions can be made about the affixes -cha / -larcha / -chasiga, -an, -ona:

a) -larcha, -chasiga affixes developed on the basis of the form -cha, which has a characteristic feature of the -cha affix, however, as a result of the separate development of these complex affixes have acquired a specific nature, methodological differences;

b) affixes *-cha / -larcha / -chasiga* serve to create new speech words in Uzbek language;

c) all words with the affix *-an* are considered to be original words from the point of view of the Uzbek language and do not require analysis and interpretation;

g) The Persian-Tajik affix *-ona*, in contrast to the *-an* form, participates in the formation of new artificial words in the Uzbek language. Although the *-ona* affix is not among the active word-formers, this affix can be rated as moderately productive. In this case, the names of individuals serve as a basis for making.

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